

ENVIRONMENTAL DEGRADATION OF GLASS-VINYLESTER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

FRP materials have assumed a paramount importance in various structural applications ranging from aerospace and defense applications to automotive, sporting goods, construction and transportation. These breakthroughs have been achieved through better design practice and innovative manufacturing processes, in addition to a greater understanding of the mechanisms governing the performance of these materials. However the developed expertises have been mainly limited to one composite material system, i.e., epoxy based composite materials. For emerging applications, such as the rehabilitation of civil engineering structures and the oil industry, this material system is not cost effective when compared to conventional materials. Glass vinylester composites are considered as potential material systems offering enhanced mechanical properties at a competitive cost. However, successful implementation of these material systems requires investigation of the long-term performance of these materials when they are subject to environmental degradation. In this paper, the long-term performance of fiber-reinforced composites based on vinylester resin is evaluated when exposed to environmental degradation induced by continuous exposure to high temperature and moisture.

KEYWORDS: Glass vinylester composites, environmental degradation, and mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

New applications are emerging for composite materials in areas such as the rehabilitation of civil infrastructures, oil exploration and marine structures, where demand for light weight, custom design and cost-effectiveness makes necessary the consideration of alternative manufacturing processes such as vacuum infusion suitable for large size structures. Resin systems such as vinylesters are known for their ease of processing owing to their low viscosity. In addition, when compared to conventional polyesters, they exhibit a higher level of environmental resistance than conventional polyesters. However, there is very little data on their long-term behavior, especially when exposed to harsh climatic conditions and corrosive fluids. This fact suggest that the issue of durability, hence prediction of long-term properties and residual life, may be a determinant factor in the success of the referred applications. The long-term behavior of composite materials may be affected by physical (e.g. changing in T_g) and chemical ageing (change in molecular, oxidation, change in density of reticulation). In fact, the swelling, the plasticization and the slow hydrolysis (with scission) of the resin, and the slow attack of the liquid on the fiber/resin interface correspond to a loss of properties with influence on the creep and fatigue behavior of composite materials [1].

This work investigates the performance of vinyl ester based composites when exposed to environmental degradation caused by high temperature and moisture absorption. This is done in order to set up design guidelines and working standards for emerging applications such as the civil engineering market and the oil industry, that will accommodate the local harsh environmental conditions.

After this introduction, a review of current research is presented, followed by material and experimental set-up. Finally, the results are analyzed and discussed with emphasis on the changes taking place on the micro-structural level through the use of electron microscopy.

Mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites such as FRP significantly depend on moisture absorption and temperature [2]. Therefore, the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and coefficient of moisture expansion (CME) are used as common design parameters for polymeric matrix based composites [3].

As mentioned above, CTE and CME are common design parameters for polymeric matrix based fiber reinforced composites. The dissimilarity between thermal and mass diffusion rates means that time is an important variable in the measurement of moisture induced dimensional change. Thermal diffusivity magnitude is many orders of magnitude greater than mass diffusivity, and therefore, greater care is required to achieve equilibrium condition (moisture versus temperature). However, short-term strain and moisture absorption data give a good approximation of the equilibrium. Thermal and/or moisture cycling may cause changes in sample porosity, micro-cracking and debonding at the fiber/matrix interface. These effects should exhibit increased moisture desorption with a lesser effect on dimensional changes, hence a lower CME.

Resistance of composite specimens to delamination fracture [4] was characterized in terms of critical strain energy release rate: G_c . For some composite systems, G_c varies considerably with the fracture mode as well as with the fiber direction of the adjacent plies with respect to the crack propagation. The results obtained show that the moisture absorption of this composite system can be well described by Fick's Law. In general, the apparent flexural Young's modulus and fracture toughness decrease with increased moisture content.

E-glass/vinyl ester composite coupons [5] with a single edge flaw were conditioned for periods of up to 7900 h at room temperature and at an elevated temperature, with and without a sustained load, to determine the changes in the tensile properties and damage mechanisms which occur with the introduction of the flaw. The early damage mechanisms were found to change from transverse matrix cracking, fiber cracking, and occasional edge delamination for unnotched specimens to the growth of a significant matrix crack from the notch tip and well defined longitudinal tow debonding for notched specimens.

The effects of hygrothermal aging on the durability of a graphite/epoxy woven composite material system were investigated [6]. Changes in physical appearance, thermal analysis results, fracture surfaces and moisture diffusion behavior all supported the idea that the ageing process affected the material. However, experimental testing also showed that the initial and residual tensile properties of the aged material were virtually unaffected by the imposed environmental ageing (as compared to unaged material testing results) except when tested at elevated temperature.

Hygrothermal freeze/thaw cycling exposures were performed on glass/vinyl ester composites to simulate the harsh temperature and moisture conditions the composites might encounter during their lifetime in service. Moisture absorption of the composite during the exposures and the hygrothermal effects on the glass transition, thermal stability, and mechanical properties of the composite were investigated. It was found that moisture absorption of the composite showed a cyclic increase, within the freeze duration, and decrease during the thaw period, while glass transition temperature of the composite exhibited a steady increase with an increase in hygrothermal cycling duration and leveled off beyond 1000 hours of the exposure. Microstructural observation revealed that, for the composite exposed to either hygrothermal cycling or simply isothermal holding, the matrix in the fractured surface region showed a more fragmented microfeature, as compared with that without any environmental conditioning [7]. Weight gain of glass vinylester composite samples increased significantly during the early stages of hygrothermal cycling (up to 1000 hrs) and then started a reverse trend and gradually dropped to zero. This was attributed to decomposition of the resin after long time exposure. This phenomenon is known as one kind of non-fickian fluid behavior [8].

Vinyl ester resins contain large number of hydroxyl groups, which promotes absorption of moisture from the environment. Such absorption causes volumetric expansion of the matrix and hence debonding at the fiber-matrix interface. The moisture could accelerate thermal decomposition of the matrix at elevated temperatures and may result in premature failure of the whole structure. There is a direct proportional relationship between the net moisture absorption amount and the exposure time: it was found that T_g initially increased with hygrothermal cycling duration. This increase was attributed to the increase of cross-linking density resulting from post curing and oxidation of vinyl ester [8].

It is well known that ultraviolet rays cause polymer to degrade by breaking the C-C bonds, which finally create cracks and delamination in the composite structures. Artificial ultraviolet degradation

was carried out on neat vinyl ester matrix specimens [9] using an integrating sphere-based UV exposure chamber. Significant changes were observed in the bulk mechanical properties, surface chemistry, and surface morphology after 1000 and 4000 h of exposure. A transition from slightly ductile to brittle behavior was observed, along with a decrease of up to 40% in average strain to failure and a decrease of up to 60% in the average specific toughness after exposure. A significant increase in the apparent hardness of the exposed surface was accompanied by an increase in the apparent modulus of the near surface region. Morphological changes, including an increase in both the number and size of surface defects on the exposed surfaces were also observed. At this stage, the environmental degradation of fiber reinforced composites remains an open subject that deserves further investigation especially, on account of the new opportunities offered to vinyl ester based composites in the oil industry and infrastructure structures. Although tangible results were achieved, further research is needed to fully understand the mechanisms that affect the performance of these materials.

MATERIALS AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

Samples were made using the hot press molding technique. The reinforcement used was a woven roving E-glass, which is a coarse drapable fabric, in which continuous roving is woven into two mutually perpendicular directions. The reinforcement has a surface weight density of 500 g/m² and an average filament diameter of 12 μm. Each stack consists of ten plies. The samples produced were squares having an edge of 150 mm. A steel frame was used to provide the desired thickness for the stack. The resin used is a vinyl ester resin: EPOVIA RF 1001HV, which is a high-viscosity type resin, supplied by Cray Valley. The vinyl ester was promoted with 3 pph of a cobalt octoate solution and catalyzed with 1.5 pph of 50% methyl ethyl ketone peroxide. The degree of cure of the composite samples was checked using a Barcol hardness test and a value between 50 and 60 was recorded.

The samples were then divided into groups each containing thirty samples. Each of the groups was exposed to a specific environment. While some samples were exposed to a dry and hot environment, others were exposed to a hot and humid environment. All samples were exposed for three and six month periods.

TESTING AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

Different properties, such as flexural strength and modulus as well as interlaminar shear strength and impact properties, were evaluated using a three point bending test as recommended by ASTM Standard (ASTM D3039- 00). Typical results for different mechanical properties obtained are shown in Table 1.

Flexural Strength (Mpa)	575	661	625	613	640
Flexural Modulus (Mpa)	19715	22833	20383	18697	21952

Properties	Environmental Conditions				
	Virgin	Moisture		Sun	
		3 months	6 months	3 months	6 months
Glass Content (%)	76.4	76.4	74.8	76.4	76.3
Impact Strength (KJ/m ²)	68.3	64.7	62.4	68.7	65.7

Table 1: Typical results for environmental testing

ILSS(Mpa)	31.6	26.9	27.44	32.2	34.02
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When comparing the results for virgin specimens with those obtained after three months and six months period, the following observations were noted:

- ❑ For moisture and sun exposure an increase of the flexural strength was observed, which may seen at first glance to be the opposite of what we expected. In other words, some degradation of mechanical properties was anticipated. However, given the relatively short period of

exposure, the extent of degradation occurring within the specimen will not be high enough to compensate for the additional strength conferred to the specimen from post-curing. During the period of testing, temperatures of up to 48° C were reported, which led to an increase in the degree of cross linking of the matrix, thus explaining the lower results obtained during testing. For moisture, this depends on the chemical structure and the curing agent as well as the degree of cure. Therefore, the moisture (in the region this is also high because of the high temperature and rate of transpiration in the Arabian Gulf) when combined with temperature will result in higher values of flexural strength and modulus.

- Specimens exposed to moisture recorded a drop in the flexural modulus after the six month period. A difference of 10% was recorded between the values of three and six months. This can be explained by the diffusion taking place within the matrix, especially if we know that in normal conditions a protective layer (gel-coat) is applied on the laminate to stop diffusion. Furthermore, the region where these specimens were exposed, a fully saturated environment can be reached frequently. For specimens exposed to a hot and dry climate, an increase in the flexural modulus (17.4%) was recorded between the three month and six month period.
- The interlaminar shear strength values recorded for various composites specimens decreased for the specimens exposed to a humid environment and increased for specimens exposed to a hot and dry environment. The occurrence of internal micro-cracks may explain such a drop in the interlaminar shear strength values for moisture specimens.

The surfaces of fractured virgin specimens and specimens exposed to different environments were examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). This was done in order to evaluate the failure mechanisms involved. From the analysis of the fractured surfaces, it is clear that different mechanisms such as debonding, delamination and cracks growth were involved in the composite fracture.

Starting with the virgin specimens shown in Figures 1-4, the following observations can be made:

- The specimens produced have a relatively high fiber content, which may affect the quality of the interface between the fibers and matrix. For this reason, poor bonding may result at the interface between the fiber and matrix. Accordingly, layer delamination and fiber pullout are identified as the predominant failure mechanisms. Also, at higher magnification, resin spots appeared on the fiber surface, which look like blisters. At this time, it is not possible to conclude whether these spots were produced following a chemical reaction between the fiber sizing and the resin or not.

Figure 1: SEM image showing high fiber content and layer delamination

Figure 2: SEM image showing fiber pull-out

Figure 3: SEM image showing resins spots on the fiber surface

Figure 4: *Distribution of resin spots over the surface of the fiber.*

For specimens exposed to a high temperature and a wet environment, a similar phenomenon was observed, although with a severe degree of degradation. It looks, as if once long-term exposure starts affecting the surface, micro-cracks present at the surface will facilitate water absorption within the matrix, which will lead to layers debonding as shown in Figure 5 and will ultimately cause composite failure. Although the conditioning period was relatively short when compared to similar work performed elsewhere, the environment prevailing here represents the extreme service conditions for a material. Consequently, the combined effects of temperature (UV rays) and a fully saturated environment will result in a rapid deterioration of the composite specimen.

Figure 5: *SEM images showing composite layers debonding.*

A different scenario was observed for specimens exposed to a high temperature and a dry environment. Here further consolidation of the specimens took place, thus resulting in higher mechanical properties, as shown in Table 1. The image of the fractured specimen (figure 6) shows micro-cracks extending through the composite layers. The combined action of resin shrinkage and resin spots could initiate and accelerate the propagation of the micro-cracks. Although a strong bond

exists at the interface between the fiber and the matrix as shown in Figure 7, thus suggesting that failure will take place mainly through layer delamination.

Figure 6: SEM image showing micro-cracks spreading through composite layers

Figure 7: SEM image showing the quality of bonding between fiber and matrix

CONCLUSION

This work was concerned with the evaluation of the long-term performance of fiber reinforced composites based on vinyl ester resin when exposed to environmental degradation. Although the duration of exposure cannot be classified as a long-term exposure, it was possible to obtain some results by accelerating the degradation process through exposure to severe environmental conditions. Accordingly a trend for the material performance when exposed to environmental conditions was established.

Specimens were divided into different groups that were subjected to different environments and exposure times. Then testing was performed using a three point bending test. Results of conditioned specimens were compared to virgin specimens to assess the extent of composite degradation. After reviewing the results and SEM images of fractured specimens, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Specimens exposed to high temperatures and a fully saturated environment were subject to degradation caused by water diffusion through the matrix. Obviously, longer conditioning periods will accelerate the initiation and propagation of the micro-cracks present at the surface, thus contributing to the diffusion process taking place within the matrix. Such an effect was confirmed by lower interlaminar shear strength values. Also poor bonding between the fiber and the matrix may accelerate composite degradation, since it results in lower values of interlaminar shear strength.
- Specimens exposed to high temperatures and a completely dry environment show a decrease in the mechanical properties after the three month period, although the variation (5%) was within the accepted range; while for the six month period, values recorded for the mechanical properties were higher than those recorded with the virgin specimens. A possible explanation is that post-cure was fully achieved after the six month period, thus providing high strength to the composite. Actually, visual observation of the specimens showed a discoloration of the composite: the original green resin changed to light yellow, which could be interpreted as resulting from further resin cross linking.

Obviously, exposure and conditioning time was not long enough to elucidate all the mechanisms affecting the degradation of fiber reinforced composites based on vinyl ester resins when exposed to severe environmental conditions. However, through initial results and observations, it was possible to recognize the main mechanisms involved in the degradation process. Furthermore, processing and conditioning of the composite samples may drastically affect the performance of the composite.

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